

**PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF INTERNATIONALIZATION OF THE
PROFESSIONAL-METHODICAL TRAINING OF THE FUTURE
ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHER**

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Abstract: This thesis discusses the internationalization of professional-methodical training of future English language teachers in the process of higher education.

Key words: individual level, professional-methodical training, internationalization, globalization, foreign languages, strategy.

Introduction:

Much of modern higher education is engaged in international activities, but this is usually the simplest, most basic level of internationalization. Internationalization of higher education at a high level can be considered as a process of systematic integration of the international component into education, research and social activities of higher educational institutions. In this sense, many, even from major centers of academic learning, cannot be considered truly international.

Higher education of the 21st century has a number of characteristics and requires certain changes in the content and organization of education. Changes are an integral part of development. Technical innovations lead to changes in technological processes, changes in the management of these processes, and changes in the training of specialists. This has always been the case, but at the end of the 20th century, the scale and speed of these changes increased so much that it was necessary to create a system for managing these changes. At the beginning of the 21st century, change has become one of the most important requirements for the successful operation of organizations, and change management has become a valuable skill of a leader.

The main factor driving changes in the field of education is the rapid increase in the flow of information. This growth is happening so fast that the previous methods and education system itself can no longer cope with it. A simple increase in the amount of acquired knowledge leads to an excessive increase in the educational load, negatively affects the health of students, but does not give the desired results. At such a rate of change, knowledge is updated so quickly that after graduating from the university, the knowledge acquired by

students has time to become obsolete. There is a need for constant updating of professional knowledge, i.e. continuous, "*lifelong*" training.

Changes in the educational environment, professional reorientation of specialists at different stages of their careers, mastering new fields of activity, career change. The students themselves have also changed — in addition to yesterday's schoolchildren, mature professionals have come to the university, become burdened with family, and combine studies with work. Their practical experience, special conditions for education force universities to change the teaching schedule and methods. It is no longer enough to convey a certain amount of knowledge to students, it has become very important to learn to search and analyze the necessary information, to teach the process of acquiring knowledge.

These changes, which are specific to the educational process, take place against the background of broader processes of change that cover individual countries, regions, and the world economy as a whole. Students study abroad and apply their knowledge by working in international companies around the world. The European Union has developed special scholarships and programs that encourage students to study abroad. Up to 80% of students in leading universities of Great Britain, USA, Canada are foreign citizens.

The rapid development of modern information technologies and distance education has made national borders absolutely transparent for educational services. A single global educational market has been formed, where universities from different countries offer their products and services to all students at the same time, without limiting themselves to national borders. Popular rankings of the best business schools of the Financial Times include not only the USA, but also Canada, Spain, France, and Great Britain. Employers in many European countries are increasingly focusing on the experience of studying, living and working abroad when hiring university graduates, as this is evidence of candidates' flexibility, breadth of worldview, and communication skills with representatives of different cultures. will give.

The main forms of internationalization of professional-methodical training of future English language teachers in the process of higher education.

The historical development of the world higher education system, the national isolation of universities is increasingly clashing with the consequences and prospects of internationalization and globalization. This main conflict is manifested in various issues and problems: recognition of university diplomas, specializations and assessments, development of international forms of quality

assessment, issues of international accreditation. In order to propose real steps to overcome this conflict, you need to analyze the main forms and characteristics, problems and prospects of the internationalization of higher education.

Professional-methodical mobility of students.

The most popular form of internationalization of higher education is student mobility - the departure of a certain number of students to study abroad. Of course, sending students to study abroad is not a new phenomenon, and some regions have been dealing with it for a long time. Many European countries have had a steady flow of students from their former colonies for many years. A large number of young people from Latin American countries are seeking degrees in the US and Canadian universities. During the Cold War, universities in the Soviet Union and Eastern Europe attracted students from countries with similar ideologies. Over the past 40 years, the rate of growth in the flow of students crossing national borders for higher education has outstripped the rate of diffusion of higher education.

Student mobility is encouraged by various national and regional programs. Many countries have bilateral and multilateral agreements in this area. The most popular European programs are Erasmus, then (since 1995) Socrates. The Erasmus program (*started in 1987 to help create a common market in Europe*) and related mobility schemes such as Comet, Lingua, etc. aim to create a European model of higher education.

On the other hand, national differences in educational opportunities, quantitative restrictions on the recruitment of students in certain specialties force students from these countries to look for opportunities to study abroad. Language and cultural considerations attract students to study programs in Great Britain, France, and the United States. The predominance of English as the primary and most studied second language in modern science has seen Canada and Australia top the list of countries receiving the most international students, along with the United States and the United Kingdom. In a number of countries, the demand for the educational programs of the universities of these countries attracts their educational services through the distribution channel: specialized agencies and consulting companies, both national and international, act as intermediaries and consultants to meet this demand.

Internationalization of educational programs.

Changes to university programs have always been met with resistance in the academic environment. Woodrow Wilson, as president of Princeton

University, said, "It is easier to move cemeteries than to change curricula." This statement aphoristically reflected the main contradiction in the development of higher education at the current stage. On the one hand, realizing the need to adapt to the complex process of constant and rapid updating of knowledge, universities strive to improve their educational programs and offer the newest fields of knowledge. On the other hand, tradition is still highly valued in education, and the fact that some attributes of higher education remain unchanged is a hallmark of the high quality of the programs offered. Many universities try to trace their history, if possible, connect their emergence with the oldest educational institutions. In the service sector, the service provider's time in the market, his reputation and name have always been the basis of confidence in the quality of the services he offers. In the field of educational services, that is, services related to the transfer of knowledge, these quality criteria are even more valuable.

A strong incentive for the internationalization of educational programs is the increasing influence of international professional associations. The rapid growth of international trade in professional services has encouraged many professions to organize their activities internationally. These professional associations have taken seriously issues such as quality assurance, minimum standard requirements, criteria for professionalism, accreditation, etc. Architects, psychologists, accountants and others are trying to develop international standards that will lead to more consistency in curriculum and quality criteria. Often such professional standards are implemented by international organizations.

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